

Looking for a favorable central place for the Establishment of Educational and Health Care Centre to equally facilitate both genders in taluka Kunri of district Umerkot, Sindh Pakistan

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Abstract : Population in rural areas are scattered in the form of different villages or settlements. The proper selection of land to launch any educational or health activities to equally facilitate both the genders is the sticky situation, both for Govt. and Private organizations. Govt. spends substantial funds for the establishment of education institution/health centre at the place which is feasible and accessible to general public. However for specific gender, the gender population is also considered so that both the gender may be benefited equally. In this research, efforts have been made to illustrate how one can choose or locate the best central place/ area in Taluka Kunri of district Umerkot Sindh Pakistan where the Educational or Health activity is to be initiated. For the purpose the concept of centre of mass theorem is used as a tool to develop mathematical model, subsequently utilize in achieving the objectives.

Keywords : Centre of mass theorem, Gender population of Taluka Kunri of District Umerkot, Graphical interpretation of town committee/villages, Establishment of Technical/ vocational / Health Care Centre.

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